

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Production performance of Holstein cows at 4 stages of lactation fed 4 dietary crude protein concentrations

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Supplementary Figure S1. Graphical description of the approach used to obtain the dietary CP concentration at the maximum predicted response (panel A) and the 95% confidence interval for the maximal response (panel B). In panel A, the dietary CP associated with the maximal response (indicated by the letter “c”) is determined as dietary CP for which the first derivative of the function equal 0; In panel B, the solid vertical line is the standard error of the maximal response and the letters “a” and “b” are the lower and upper limits of the 95% confidence interval, respectively.